

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CONCEPTUAL METAPHOR IN PEDAGOGICAL DISCOURSE (USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE CONCEPTUAL AREAS OF TEACHER-STUDENT)

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Abstract

Pedagogical metaphorology in Russia is just beginning to take shape as an autonomous scientific discipline. Conceptual metaphors are studied mainly from the standpoint of their relevance in pedagogical communication, the effectiveness of educational influence, and the importance for the assimilation of educational material. The purpose of this article is to identify conceptual metaphors with new conceptual areas of teacher-student, representing the main subjects of pedagogical discourse.

Keywords: cognitive-discursive paradigm, pedagogical discourse, pedagogical metaphorology, conceptual metaphor, original conceptual domain, new conceptual domain, metaphorical mapping, teacher, student

In the light of the modern cognitive-discursive paradigm, the conceptual metaphor attracts special attention of researchers.

The conceptual metaphor is based on a metaphorical mapping, that is, a stable correspondence between the original and the new conceptual areas based on the common semantic-cognitive feature of various objects of reality, similar in analog-associative terms [7].

The essential difference between the original conceptual domain and the new conceptual domain is that the source of the formation of the original conceptual domain is the physical and bodily experience of a person. This area is fundamental, it is characterized by accuracy and anthropocentricity, therefore it is of paramount importance for the orientation of a person in the world [6]. As for the new conceptual domain, it has a secondary character. The knowledge associated with it is often not the result of direct observation, but the consequence of human mental activity, therefore it has a more abstract character, which determines the need for the emergence of a so-called conceptual metaphor capable of filling lexical and semantic gaps.

Thus, a conceptual metaphor arises as a result of a cognitive operation, a comparison of mental images of two different objects or phenomena, the discovery of similarities and differences in them, since there are two mental zones in the minds of speakers (the original and the new conceptual areas), the components of which enter into a complex interaction in the process of metaphorization.

The research devoted to the conceptual metaphor in pedagogical discourse was conducted by domestic and foreign linguists (J. Grady, L. Cameron, D. Allbritton, E.G. Kabachenko, S.A. Khakhalova, A.P. Chudinov, E.V. Budaev, etc.).

Pedagogical metaphorology interprets, models, predicts conceptual metaphors of pedagogical discourse, reflecting its essential foundations.

Conceptual metaphors should be considered as multilevel and multifunctional models of thought-speech. In pedagogical discourse, they, firstly, are the visual and figurative embodiment of various aspects of pedagogical activity and allow to reveal hidden deep

(archetypal) mechanisms of interaction between teacher and student. Secondly, metaphors reflect the ideals and values of pedagogical discourse, fix its various aspects and parameters, models and strategies. Thirdly, metaphors describe the features of consciousness, worldview, behavior of participants in pedagogical discourse, the specifics of the educational and (more broadly) educational process. Fourth, metaphors provide continuity and consistency of pedagogical experience, while exposing contradictions, inconsistencies of ideal and real ideas about pedagogical and student activity [8].

We have considered conceptual metaphors, the new conceptual areas of which are the participants of pedagogical interaction – the teacher and the student.

The following metaphors are in the focus of the metaphorical representation of learning from the teacher's position:

1. A TEACHER is a GARDENER

The teacher is identified with the gardener: he takes care of the children as if they were flowers in the garden.

2. A TEACHER is a COACH

A teacher-coach is different from a teacher-gardener. The coach places high hopes on their students and pushes them to go beyond their capabilities.

3. THE TEACHER is a JUGGLER

Learning is a multitasking process. Obviously, it is difficult to cope with a class consisting of 20-30 students. In addition, each child has different abilities, learning styles and needs: several students will finish their work overtime; others will not be able to understand the topic and they will need an additional explanation; others do not get along with each other and need to be kept in different directions in the classroom. The list goes on: the teacher needs to juggle all these diverse needs and requirements at the same time.

4. THE TEACHER is a SCULPTOR

At the beginning of the school year, the teacher receives students whose views on certain issues are chaotic. But during the year, children acquire deeper knowledge in various subjects and it can be traced that they become "more reasonable". Ideas in their minds

begin to "take shape". The work of a teacher is very similar to the work of a sculptor.

5. A TEACHER is a DOCTOR

Sometimes teachers need to "diagnose" a variety of topics. Just as a doctor should take into account all factors affecting the patient, teachers should monitor all factors that may cause learning difficulties. This can be a powerful signal for a teacher who needs to be considered a professional who identifies and diagnoses the problems that students face.

Thus, conceptual metaphors with the new conceptual domain of the TEACHER help to better understand the various roles, tasks and responsibilities of the teacher.

Now let's consider conceptual metaphors with the new conceptual sphere of the STUDENT.

1. A STUDENT is a BABY

A student is like a child learning to crawl. This metaphor refers to students who are at the very beginning of their learning journey. They have a long way to go and every stage of the learning process is important.

2. THE STUDENT is A BLANK SLATE

The blank slate metaphor was coined by John Locke. Locke used the Latin term "tabula rasa", which means "blank sheet" in English. Locke was a Scottish philosopher who believed that children are born with empty thoughts. They are like blank boards, ready for knowledge to be written on them. Nowadays, many people disagree with Locke. Students have families, friends, and cultural traditions that they rely on to make sense of the world. We all have a history, which means that we are not blank sheets.

3. THE DISCIPLE is a FLOWER

In the process of learning, the individual grows as a person. He acquires wisdom and develops skills.

4. The STUDENT is a SPONGE

This metaphor is especially relevant in preschool education. Young children have the ability to absorb everything around them. This metaphor shows how important guided practice is. Guided practice means that teachers are role models. They model behavior, actions, and skills whenever a student is in their field of vision.

5. A STUDENT is a RESEARCHER

Treating a student as a researcher is another great way to explain a difficult topic. This metaphor shows how learning can be exciting.

6. A STUDENT is a SCULPTOR

Sculptors start with a piece of clay and chip it away until they create a work of art. Similarly, students begin with a general idea of the topic. As they learn more about it, they begin to have a versatile look.

7. A STUDENT is a TRAVELER

This metaphor is especially relevant in literature, history and geography lessons. The student learns about

representatives of different communities and cultures other than his own.

8. THE DISCIPLE is an EMPTY VESSEL

The metaphor of an empty vessel depicts students with empty heads, ready to be filled with knowledge. Many teachers consider the metaphor with an empty vessel too simplistic: we do not just accumulate new knowledge in our mind. We actively construct knowledge in our head.

9. A STUDENT is a DRIVER

Previously, we thought that students passively listen as the teacher transmits knowledge. But nowadays we think of the student as an active subject responsible for his own development. Instead of the teacher who directs the lesson, the student is the driver. The teacher takes on the role of navigator in the front seat, giving advice and support when needed.

Thus, pedagogical metaphorology is a symbolic mirror of pedagogical reality. Conceptual metaphors reflect ideas about the leading participants of pedagogical interaction – teachers and students.

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